

Stress Analysis of Mouldboard Ploughs Using the Finite Element Method

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Abstract

Mouldboard ploughs are fundamental implements in agricultural production and widely used in primary tillage. The share and mouldboard are designed to cut and invert soil, which subjects the plough to significant structural stresses, especially in components directly contacting the soil. In this study, the mechanical behavior of a five-bottom mouldboard plough during tillage was modeled and analyzed in three dimensions, considering both embedded and aboveground parts. The plough was precisely modeled in SolidWorks, and stress analysis was conducted using ANSYS Workbench with the finite element method (FEM). The analysis mesh consisted of 1,034,489 tetrahedral elements and 1,811,369 nodes, with three-point hitch connections fixed as boundary conditions. Draft forces up to 1131.4 N, obtained from manufacturer data, were applied to the share tips. Stress distributions under dynamic loading conditions were evaluated in detail. The analysis revealed that all plough components operated within the yield strength limits of their materials, maintaining structural integrity. The maximum equivalent (von Mises) stress occurred at the front hitch bracket (493.53 MPa), with safety factors across critical regions ranging from 1.67 to 34.89. Maximum displacement was 7.69 mm. Localized increases in stress intensity, particularly at connection points, were observed and thoroughly analyzed. Safety factors were determined for components both in and out of the soil, establishing the system's overall reliability. These results highlight the practical value of advanced numerical simulations in optimizing the weight, safety, and performance of agricultural machinery by identifying critical stress regions and guiding design improvements.

Keywords: Plough, finite element method, dynamic loading, structural optimization, agricultural machinery

1. Introduction

The agricultural production process is a multi-stage activity that requires the management of numerous complex biophysical factors. The most fundamental and decisive initial step in this process is the preparation of the seedbed. Considering the variations in cropping patterns depending on plant species, seeds need to be sown at different depths. However, successful root development at these depths depends not only on biological factors but also on the establishment of physically suitable conditions. In this context, the physical structure of both the soil surface and its sublayers must be regulated. This includes the simultaneous fulfillment of multiple conditions such as the reduction of soil compaction, ensuring homogeneous moisture distribution, enhancing aeration capacity, and improving soil structure. To achieve these goals, the primary mechanical method employed is soil tillage, and among the most commonly used implements in this process are moldboard ploughs. Moldboard ploughs hold a significant place in the historical development of soil tillage technology. These implements have effectively fulfilled functions such as burying surface residues, inverting the soil, and aerating it, thereby facilitating the transition from traditional farming to modern agriculture. Today, they remain among the most widely used and essential tools in agricultural machinery. In particular, the elimination of soil compaction caused by repeated field traffic during the previous farming season makes the functionality of these plows indispensable. This is because compacted soil negatively affects both water infiltration and root development, directly reducing crop yield. Consequently, the mechanical tillage of soil has become a necessary practice. Therefore, the role of moldboard plows in agricultural production is not limited to seedbed preparation; they are also utilized to meet one of the fundamental requirements of organic farming—weed control (Yalcin et al., 2006; Godwin et al., 2007; Chaudhary et al., 1985; Azimi-Nejadian et al., 2019; Azimi-Nejadian et al., 2022;

Arslan et al., 2006; Akıncı et al., 1994). Since the use of chemical herbicides is either prohibited or strictly limited in organic agriculture, mechanical soil tillage becomes a critical practice for managing weed populations. In this context, the moldboard plow serves as a versatile tool, contributing to both physical and environmental sustainability. However, the effective use of moldboard ploughs is directly related to their draft force requirements. Due to their high draft resistance, operating such equipment requires powerful tractors. This leads to increased energy consumption and, consequently, higher production costs. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the forces exerted by ploughs on the soil, accurate prediction of draft force requirements, and optimal tractor-implement matching are of great importance in the management of agricultural mechanization. In this regard, numerous researchers have developed various modeling and measurement techniques to accurately predict moldboard plow draft force. For instance, Oskoui et al. (1982) analyzed the influence of cone index (CI) and soil bulk density on the draft force of moldboard ploughs by measuring these parameters in different soil zones. Expanding on this work, Oskoui and Witney (1982) proposed that draft force should not only be evaluated using CI and bulk density, but also in conjunction with variables such as forward speed and share cutting angle. The mathematical model they proposed was tested through field trials conducted across a wide range of soil moisture contents, and a high level of agreement was observed between predicted and actual results—strongly supporting the model's validity and reliability. Developed comprehensive empirical models to predict the draft requirements of tillage implements using orthogonal and multiple regression techniques. Their models demonstrated a high correlation between predicted draft forces and measured data. On the other hand, Arvidsson and Keller (2011) emphasized that conventional penetrometer measurements are insufficient for predicting draft force and instead proposed empirical models based on the direct

relationship between soil cohesion and draft force. Their findings revealed that soil cohesion was more strongly correlated with draft force than penetration resistance, highlighting the need for selecting more accurate parameters in draft force prediction studies. In addition, recent advances in engineering have enabled the effective use of numerical simulation techniques in the design and performance analysis of agricultural machinery. Advanced modeling methods such as the Discrete Element Method (DEM) and Finite Element Method (FEM) allow the simulation of soil-machine interaction in three dimensions and over time. This makes it possible to conduct virtual field trials at significantly lower cost, independently of time, and with high repeatability. Some pioneering studies in this field include the work of, who proposed numerical modeling approaches to overcome the limitations of analytical and experimental methods. Azimi Nejadian et al. (2019), and Ucgul et al. (2015, 2017) successfully applied DEM to simulate the interaction between moldboard ploughs and soil. Gupta et al. (2016) employed a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian technique to simulate the soil cutting process in Abaqus/Explicit using the Mohr-Coulomb yield function and obtained results in good agreement with experimental shear vane measurements. FEM has also been applied in the modeling of specific applications such as the cone penetration test. Studies in this area (Upadhyaya et al., 1984; Tekeste et al., 2007; Tekeste et al., 2009; Gupta et al., 2015; Kok et al., 1996; Korucu et al., 2003; Kerenyi et al., 2002) have demonstrated that FEM can provide high accuracy in modeling and analyzing the mechanical properties of soil. When simulation results were compared with field data, the differences were observed to be minimal. All these studies indicate that the effective use of engineering design tools not only improves machine performance but also significantly reduces production costs. However, a large proportion of small-scale manufacturers continue to rely on traditional design methods due to limited access to analytical tools and a lack of technical

knowledge. As a result, they often design oversized and unnecessarily heavy moldboard ploughs. This leads to material waste and inefficient energy use. Therefore, engineering analyses based on optimal design principles make it possible to develop lighter, more economical, and more efficient plough structures. One notable study in this context used FEM to perform stress analysis on a three-bottom moldboard plough. The regions subjected to excessive stress were identified, and it was concluded that a 17.6% material saving could be achieved in the chassis and beam cross-sections. Similarly, validated their FEM results by comparing them with experimental data. Kerenyi et al. conducted stress analysis on two different plough models and found high consistency between field measurements and FEM data. Plouffe et al., through numerical simulations, reported that the longitudinal (X-axis) forces were 1.4 and 2.7 times greater than the vertical (Y-axis) and lateral (Z-axis) forces, respectively. This indicates that reducing the tillage depth can result in a 16% decrease in draft force and an 8% reduction in fuel consumption. Despite these advances, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding the comprehensive three-dimensional finite element analysis of multi-bottom mouldboard ploughs under realistic field boundary conditions, with detailed assessment of stress concentrations, displacement, and safety factors across all critical components. Previous studies have either focused on single or simplified plough models, or did not integrate real field loading scenarios and material properties with high-fidelity simulation setups. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to perform a detailed three-dimensional FEM-based stress and displacement analysis of a five-bottom mouldboard plough, incorporating actual field load conditions, precise CAD modeling, and advanced meshing strategies. This work provides new insights by quantifying the maximum stress values, safety factors, and deformation under realistic loading, which are essential for design validation and optimization. The findings not only address a critical research gap but also offer practical

guidance for manufacturers and engineers aiming to improve the structural performance, safety, and cost-effectiveness of agricultural tillage machinery.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Geometric modeling

The research material examined in this study is a five-bottom mouldboard plough, a widely used implement in modern agricultural practices. The plough was modeled with high geometric accuracy in SolidWorks, a computer-aided design (CAD) software. Each component, including the share, mouldboard,

landside, body plate, connection plates, and supporting chassis, was modeled individually and then assembled to form the complete plough system. This precise digital model serves as the basis for finite element analysis, ensuring that the simulation reflects real-world geometries and assembly structures. The plough was designed as a three-point hitch implement, and mounting points were fully fixed in the finite element model to simulate field constraints. This solid model formed the basis for subsequent finite element analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Three-dimensional CAD model of the five-bottom mouldboard plough

2.2. Material properties

Two different steel grades were used for the plough components:

- The share, which directly contacts and cuts through the soil, was made of 30MnB5 alloy steel, known for its high wear resistance, toughness, and hardenability.

- The remaining structural components (mouldboard, body, frame, etc.) were manufactured from standard construction steel (e.g., St37 or St52), widely used in agricultural machinery due to its good weldability and adequate strength. The mechanical properties used in the simulations are presented in Table 1, with all values double-checked for accuracy.

Table 1. Material properties of the moldboard plough components

Moldboard plough share (30MnB5)	Properties	Structural Component (5630 Steel)	Properties
Young's Modulus	210 GPa	Young's Modulus	210 GPa
Yield Strength	510 MPa	Yield Strength	825 MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.3	Poisson's Ratio	0.3
Density	7860 kg/m ³		

2.3. Boundary conditions

The plough was modeled as mounted to the tractor via a three-point hitch system. In the finite element model, these hitch points were fully fixed to simulate actual field constraints, while the remainder of the plough was allowed to deform freely under load. The five-bottom moldboard plow examined within the scope of this research was designed as a solid model using SolidWorks, one of the computer-aided three-dimensional (3D) modeling software programs (Figure 2). A detailed three-dimensional solid model of the five-bottom mouldboard plough was created using SolidWorks (Figure 1). All main components were individually modeled and assembled to ensure geometric accuracy for the subsequent finite element analysis (FEA). The completed

CAD model was exported in STEP format and imported into ANSYS Workbench, where three-dimensional linear static analyses were performed. The plough was discretized into tetrahedral elements, with mesh refinement applied to high-stress regions to ensure accurate results. Loading and boundary conditions were determined using field data and previous studies. In the simulations, only horizontal draft forces—calculated using the empirical formula by Acar et al. (2011) were applied to the share tips, as vertical forces were considered negligible. In that study, the draft force acting on each plow body was calculated using Equation (1), which depends on the physical properties of the soil and the geometry of the plough. These outputs provide valuable insights for improving both the safety and cost-effectiveness of the design.

$$R_c = a \cdot b \cdot n \cdot k_o \cdot \sqrt{v} \quad (1)$$

In the equation:

R_c : Draft force (daN)

a : Working depth (dm)

b : Working width of a single bottom (dm)

n : Number of bottoms (units)

k_o : Specific soil resistance (kp/dm²) A

value of 70 kp/dm² was chosen for specific

soil resistance, as it represents typical conditions for medium-textured agricultural soils (taken as 70 kp/dm² in this study).

v : Forward speed (km/h) (A value of 3.6 km/h was used in this study).

Figure 2. Solid model drawings of the moldboard plough

2.4. Meshing process

The assembled 3D model was imported into ANSYS Workbench and discretized using tetrahedral solid elements. A finer mesh was applied to regions prone to stress concentration, such as sharp corners and connection areas, while a coarser mesh was used elsewhere for computational efficiency. The final mesh contained 1,034,489 elements and 1,811,369 nodes, providing a good balance of accuracy and computational cost. The mesh structure is illustrated in Figure 3. This figure

illustrates the general mesh configuration of the model, clearly showing how both the plow bodies and the connecting components are discretized. In the visual, the localized mesh refinement applied to the share regions can be clearly observed. This strategy ensures that the solution is more precise in areas where stress concentrations are highest. In addition, the element types used in the model are 3D solid elements; specifically, tetrahedral structures were preferred as they allow for accurate representation of complex surface geometries.

Figure 3. Finite element mesh structure of the moldboard plough model

2.5. Loading scenarios

Draft force is the primary horizontal force that must be exerted by a tractor to enable effective operation of tillage implements in the soil. While agricultural implements are

subjected to both horizontal and vertical forces during tillage, the horizontal component—arising mainly from soil resistance—is the dominant factor affecting plough performance and structural loads. Vertical forces, mostly due to gravity, are relatively minor and do not

significantly influence the implement's movement or the analysis outcomes. Therefore, in this study, only horizontal draft forces were considered in the finite element simulations. In the finite element simulations, horizontal forces of 1131.4 N and 707.1 N were applied at the tips of the shares, opposite to the direction of motion, to represent realistic soil resistance. The force of 1131.4 N was assigned to the central body, where higher resistance occurs, while 707.1 N was applied to the outer and inner bodies, as shown in Figure 4. These loads were defined at the soil-

contacting regions, the most critical areas of the system. The careful placement and direction of each force vector were selected to accurately reflect real field conditions and to improve the reliability of the simulation. These loading configurations allowed analysis of the plough's structural behavior under demanding scenarios, with results such as stress and deformation distributions presented in Figures 5 through 9. These outcomes were used to evaluate system strength and guide design optimization.

Figure 4. Definition of boundary conditions and applied loads

Figure 5. Definition of the applied loads on the first bottom of the moldboard plough

Figure 6. Definition of the applied loads on the second bottom of the moldboard plough

Figure 7. Definition of the applied loads on the third bottom of the moldboard plough

Figure 8. Definition of the applied loads on the fourth bottom of the moldboard plough

Figure 9. Definition of the applied loads on the fifth bottom of the moldboard plough

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Stress distribution

The finite element analyses revealed the equivalent (von Mises) stress distribution throughout the plough structure. The maximum stress was observed at the front portion of the front hitch bracket, which acts as the main load transfer region between the tractor and plough (Figure 10). This region is structurally critical due to its role as the first load-bearing element in the system. The maximum equivalent stress calculated here was 493.53 MPa, remaining below the yield strength of the material and indicating sufficient structural safety under the simulated loads. Stress distributions in other components are presented in Figures 11–15. Maximum stresses in all critical parts were below the material yield strengths, as summarized in Table 2.

3.2. Safety factor calculations

The safety factor is a widely used metric in engineering design and is defined as follows:
 $n = \text{Yield strength of the material} / \text{Maximum calculated stress}$

Safety factors, defined as the ratio of material yield strength to maximum stress, are presented in Table 2. All components exhibited safety factors above critical thresholds, confirming adequate design margins. It should be noted that the safety factor for the share component (34.89) is extremely high, indicating that the current loading scenario and boundary conditions may be conservative for this part. This suggests potential for material optimization or weight reduction in the share design. The concentration of high stresses at the front hitch bracket reflects the structural load path from soil interaction to the tractor connection point.

Figure 10. Distribution of equivalent stresses across the entire structure

Figure 11. Equivalent stress distributions for the plough body

Figure 12. Equivalent stress distributions for the moldboard leg component

Figure 13. Equivalent stress distributions for the share component

Figure 14. Equivalent stress distributions for the moldboard extension component

Figure 15. Equivalent stress distributions for the moldboards

Table 2. Calculated operational safety factors for the moldboard plough

Moldboard plough components	Material yield strength $[\sigma_{yield}]$ [MPa]	Maximum equivalent stress $[\sigma_{eq}]$ [MPa]	Safety factor $[k_{sf}] = [\sigma_{yield} / \sigma_{eq}]$
Moldboards	510	161,22	3,163
Body component	825	364,09	2,266
Moldboard leg component	825	493,53	1,672
Share component	825	23,644	34,892
Moldboard extension component	825	191,99	4,297

3.3. Displacement analysis

Displacement analysis was performed to assess deformations under load (Figure 16).

The maximum total displacement was found to be 7.69 mm.

Figure 16. Maximum total displacement distribution of the moldboard plough

This displacement value is generally tolerable for agricultural machinery, which operates in direct soil contact and naturally experiences some deformation. However, in practice, a maximum displacement of 7.69 mm may cause slight variations in tillage depth, which should be considered if precise depth control is required in certain crops or soil conditions. The simulation results indicate elastic behavior, and permanent deformation is not expected under the modeled conditions.

4. Conclusion

This study presented a comprehensive engineering analysis of a five-bottom mouldboard plough using advanced CAD modeling and finite element simulations. Key results of the stress and displacement analyses are as follows:

- ✓ The maximum equivalent (von Mises) stress was 493.53 MPa, located at the front

hitch component, confirming this as the structurally critical region.

- ✓ All other major structural components exhibited maximum stress values well below their material yield strengths, as detailed in Table 2.
- ✓ The maximum displacement was 7.69 mm, indicating elastic deformation and structural stability under operational loads.

4.1. Design optimization

The calculated safety factor for the share component was extremely high (34.89), suggesting that weight reduction or material optimization is feasible without compromising structural safety.

4.2. Material selection

All selected materials provided sufficient strength; however, using high-strength steel in

the front hitch region may further improve reliability.

4.3. Practical contributions of virtual testing

The use of virtual FEM-based testing prior to prototype production enables the identification of critical stress regions, supports targeted structural improvements, and reduces both time and costs associated with physical prototyping. Numerical analysis also facilitates the evaluation of practical outcomes, such as the potential effect of observed displacement on tillage depth consistency during field operation.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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